

Modulation of Oral Microbiome by Probiotics and Prebiotics in Periodontal Disease Management

Swapna Mohanty¹
Zeba Rahman Siddique²
Sanjay Gupta³
Quazi Shefa Zaman⁴
Alina Nihal⁵

PG Student¹
Department of Periodontology and Oral Implantology
Career Postgraduate Institute of Dental Sciences
& Hospital
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India

Reader²
Department of Periodontology and Oral Implantology
Career Postgraduate Institute of Dental Sciences
& Hospital
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India

Professor & Head³
Department of Periodontology and Oral Implantology
Career Postgraduate Institute of Dental Sciences
& Hospital
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India

PG Student⁴
Department of Periodontology and Oral Implantology
Career Postgraduate Institute of Dental Sciences
& Hospital
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India

PG Student⁵
Department of Periodontology and Oral Implantology
Career Postgraduate Institute of Dental Sciences
& Hospital
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India

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Abstract

Periodontal disease is a chronic inflammatory condition initiated by dysbiosis of the oral microbiome, leading to progressive destruction of the supporting tooth structures. Current management strategies emphasize not only reducing pathogenic biofilms but also restoring microbial balance. Probiotics live microorganisms that provide health benefits when administered in sufficient amounts have emerged as a promising adjunctive therapy in periodontics. Specific strains, particularly *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium*, have demonstrated the ability to reduce periodontopathogen load, modulate host immune responses and lower proinflammatory markers. Clinical studies suggest that probiotics can improve periodontal outcomes by reducing plaque accumulation, halitosis, pocket depth, and attachment loss. Moreover, when combined with prebiotics, their efficacy may be enhanced by promoting the growth and activity of beneficial microbial species. Despite encouraging evidence, further well-designed trials are required to establish standardized protocols, optimal strains, and long-term benefits of probiotics in periodontal therapy.

Introduction

The oral cavity is home to the second largest and most diverse community of microorganisms in the human body, following the gastrointestinal tract. The discovery of microbes in dental plaque dates back to Antonie van Leeuwenhoek, who first observed them using a microscope. Since that time, dental plaque has been examined primarily through qualitative methods. Modern research indicates that the oral microbiome comprises over 250 different microbial species. Among these are several pathogens *Streptococcus mutans*, *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Tannerella forsythia*, and *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans* which play significant roles in the development of periodontal diseases.^[1]

The initial factor in the development of periodontal disease is often the accumulation of dental plaque, primarily resulting from poor oral hygiene practices.^[2] This condition is recognized as an inflammatory disorder that affects the supporting structures of the teeth, ultimately leading to the formation of periodontal pockets, gum recession, and subsequent loss of tissue attachment and alveolar bone.^[3] The cause

of periodontal disease is closely linked to bacterial plaque and is determined by three main factors: a host who is susceptible, the presence of disease-causing microbial species, and a diminished or absent population of beneficial microorganisms.^[4] In addition, the involvement of other microbes, such as fungal organisms, should not be overlooked.^[5,6]

The onset and progression of periodontal disease are driven by an imbalance in the normal oral microbiota, known as dysbiosis. This disturbance can impair the host's immune response, triggering chronic inflammation that, in individuals with a predisposition, results in irreversible damage to the periodontium, including the alveolar bone and periodontal ligament.^[7-8] Ongoing inflammation may lead to persistent periodontal pockets and the survival of harmful bacteria, which can cause continued tissue damage.^[9,10]

Current treatment approaches focus on

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modifying the ecological environment within oral niches by transforming harmful plaque into a biofilm dominated by beneficial commensal microorganisms. Probiotics live microorganisms that provide health benefits when taken in adequate amounts are gaining attention in this regard. Fermented foods and beverages containing probiotics have been consumed for hundreds of years, long before the health benefits of these microorganisms were scientifically recognized. The formal acknowledgment of probiotics as a therapeutic nutritional approach only began in the 20th century.

In 1905, French pediatrician Henry Tissier noted that infants suffering from diarrhea had fewer Bifidobacteria a type of beneficial gut bacteria in their digestive systems compared to healthy. This marked one of the first scientific observations of the potential role of gut bacteria in health.^[11] Then, in 1907, Russian scientist Elie Metchnikoff proposed that the presence of beneficial bacteria in fermented dairy products could enhance health and longevity.

The word "probiotics" was first introduced by Kollath in the 1950s and later adopted in 1965 by researchers Lilly and Stillwell.^[12] It is derived from the Latin word "pro," meaning "for," and the Greek word "bios," meaning "life," thus translating to "for life."

Often described as "probiotic nano-soldiers," certain strains can halt, alter, or slow the progression of periodontal diseases. In periodontics, probiotics show promise in managing plaque, reducing bad breath, decreasing anaerobic bacterial colonization, and improving clinical measures like pocket depth and attachment loss. The main probiotic genera involved are Lactobacillus and Bifidobacterium.

A prebiotic is defined as a selectively fermented ingredient that promotes specific changes in the composition and/or activity of the gut microbiota, ultimately benefiting the host's health and well-being.^[13] Classified as functional foods, prebiotics are resistant to degradation during cooking. Probiotics are often administered together with prebiotics in various forms like powders, sachets, gelatin capsules, or suspensions. One such combination product available in the Indian market is "BION," which contains both pre- and probiotics. Gheisary et al, 2022 in Systematic Review and Meta analysis included Prevention and treatment of periodontitis and probiotics. Prevention and treatment of periodontitis alone. The result showed that Probiotics supplementation reduces the periodontopathogen load and proinflammatory markers.^[14] Despite the promising effects of probiotics, it remains uncertain whether this adjunct therapy consistently improves periodontal disease outcomes.

Oral and Gut Microbiomes

Oral Microbiome

The human oral microbiome is the second largest, most diverse, and most complex microbial community after the gut. This unique ecosystem consists of several commensal, symbiotic, and potentially pathogenic microorganisms, including prokaryotic species, fungi, viruses, and protozoa. Fungi are an integral part of the healthy oral microbiota. They primarily

belong to six major phyla of commensal bacteria: Firmicutes, Actinobacteria, Proteobacteria, Fusobacteria, Bacteroidetes, and Spirochaetes.^[15] These microorganisms typically exist within a self-generated extracellular polymeric matrix (EPM), forming complex communities known as biofilms.

The human oral cavity contains a variety of microbial populations that are typically organized into three primary ecological zones based on differences in microbial composition: Group 1 includes surfaces such as the buccal mucosa, keratinized gingiva, and hard palate. Group 2 covers areas like saliva, the tongue, tonsils, and throat, while Group 3 is made up of microbial communities found in subgingival and supragingival plaque.^[16] The distinct microbial distribution across these regions is shaped by several environmental conditions, including pH, salinity, oxygen levels, redox potential, and available nutrients.

Among healthy individuals, the top surface of the tongue (lingual dorsum) is mainly colonized by Streptococcus salivarius, Rothia mucilaginosa, and an unclassified strain of Eubacterium.^[17] These microbial interactions encompass synergistic metabolic cooperation, intense competition for essential nutrients, horizontal gene transfer facilitating genetic adaptability, interference with intercellular signaling pathways to secure a competitive colonization advantage, and antagonism toward competing microorganisms.

Gut Microbiome

The gut microbiota is the most densely populated microbial ecosystem in the human body, with bacterial numbers increasing throughout the gastrointestinal tract and peaking in the colon, where concentrations can reach as high as 10^{12} bacteria per gram of intestinal content. The majority around 90% of these microorganisms belong to four main bacterial phyla: Firmicutes, Bacteroidetes, Proteobacteria, and Actinobacteria, collectively comprising between 500 and 1,000 distinct species. These gut bacteria are classified according to their oxygen tolerance into aerobic, anaerobic, and facultative anaerobic groups.^[18]

Oral-Gut Axis

The bidirectional interactions between the gut and oral cavity play a significant role in the development and complexity of diseases affecting both sites. Two main pathways have been proposed for the transmission of oral bacteria to the gut: the hematogenous route, where oral bacteria enter the bloodstream through lesions and travel systemically to colonize the GI mucosa and the enteral route, in which bacteria pass from the oral cavity through the stomach and into the intestines. The movement of oral pathogens to the gut via these routes can influence gut physiology and contribute to disease processes (Kitamoto et al., 2020a).

Additionally, reduced gastric acidity has been shown to alter the gut microbiota composition, shifting it toward an oral-like microbial profile. This phenomenon further supports the idea that dysfunction of the oral-gut barrier facilitates the migration of oral microbes into the gut environment. When the gut barrier is weakened, harmful gut microbes or their byproducts can enter the bloodstream and reach the alveolar

bone, and can trigger the growth of inflammatory immune cells (Th17) that migrate to the gums and inducing disease.^[19,20]

Factors Influencing Microbe Composition and Their Impact on Periodontal and Gut Pathogenesis

Factors Influencing Oral Microbes

Environmental factors play a crucial role in shaping the oral microbiome and can contribute to lifestyle-related diseases. For instance, *Porphyromonas gingivalis* is linked to increased risks of metabolic and inflammatory disorders. Obesity is associated with higher levels of harmful periodontal bacteria, while smoking exacerbates periodontitis by altering the microbial environment and weakening immune responses.^[21] Additionally, dental materials and prostheses influence biofilm formation, with rough surfaces promoting bacterial growth. Dietary factors are particularly influential. A diet with reduced vitamins and micronutrients increases periodontal disease severity. Omega-3 fatty acids support periodontal therapy by reducing pocket depth and improving attachment. Vitamin C is essential for preventing gum bleeding and inflammation.^[21]

Factors Influencing Gut Microbes

Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) is a multifactorial condition involving genetic susceptibility, immune dysfunction, and gut microbiota imbalance. High-fat diets and microbial shifts further contribute to disease onset and progression.

Microbe Modulation to Treat Periodontitis

The primary treatment for periodontal disease remains scaling and root planing, a mechanical method to remove plaque and calculus from tooth surfaces (Drisko, 2014). To manage microbial imbalance, broad-spectrum antimicrobial mouthwashes like chlorhexidine are commonly used. Additional non-antibiotic therapies include metal compounds, photodynamic therapy, vaccines, and various host-modulating agents such as disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs), statins, probiotics, bisphosphonates, omega-3 fatty acids (n-3 PUFAs), specialized pro-resolving mediators (SPMs), and complement inhibitors. These agents help reduce inflammation and support tissue healing.

Synbiotics

Synbiotics are combinations of probiotics and prebiotics that provide complementary benefits. While probiotics mainly act in the small intestine and prebiotics in the large intestine, their combination can create a synergistic effect. The concept was introduced by Gibson et al. in 1995 and refined by ISAPP in 2020 to describe mixtures that support the host's native microbiota. In oral health, a formulation combining 2% L-arginine with *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* significantly reduced *Streptococcus mutans* biofilm formation and limited acid production, maintaining a stable pH.^[22]

Prebiotics

Prebiotics were initially defined in 1995. In 2017, the International Scientific Association for Probiotics and Prebiotics (ISAPP) updated the definition to "a substrate that is selectively utilized by host microorganisms, providing a health benefit."

Urea: when metabolized by urease-producing bacteria such as *Streptococcus salivarius*, *Actinomyces naeslundii*, and *Haemophilus* species, produces ammonia and bicarbonate.

These byproducts help neutralize acids in the oral environment, promoting a healthier pH balance. Similarly, nitrate-reducing bacteria in the mouth convert dietary nitrate into nitrite, which is further reduced to nitric oxide a compound known to inhibit the growth of harmful periodontal pathogens.^[23]

Arginine: It supports the production of alkaline substances, helping to prevent tooth demineralization and inhibit the formation of harmful biofilms. Arginine also shows antifungal activity. Additionally, L-arginine boosts the activity of alkali-generating bacteria such as *Streptococcus sanguinis* and *S. gordonii*, creating a less favorable environment for acid-producing, cariogenic microorganisms.

Postbiotics

Postbiotics, defined by ISAPP in 2021, are preparations of non-living microorganisms or their components that confer health benefits. Also called paraprobiotics or bacterial lysates, postbiotics are stable under heat and pH changes, easier to store, and pose fewer safety concerns. They can be integrated into toothpaste, chewing gum, or oral supplements. While postbiotics may have reduced adhesion or antimicrobial activity compared to live probiotics e.g., heat-treated *Lactobacillus reuteri*.

Probiotics

With growing concerns over antibiotic resistance and the persistence of infectious diseases such as gastroenteritis, interest in probiotics has intensified, highlighting their potential as a natural and effective complement to traditional therapies. Today, the World Health Organization and the Food and Agriculture Organization define probiotics as "live microorganisms which, when administered in adequate amounts, confer a health benefit on the host." Probiotics have shown potential in preventing and managing oral diseases such as dental caries, gingivitis, and periodontitis. In dentistry, commonly used strains include *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium*.

Arbildo- Vega et al, 2021 in Systematic review and meta-analysis used *Lactobacillus reuteri* + mechanical debridement Mechanical debridement alone. They found that PPD improvement has been observed in the group using *Lactobacillus Reuteri*.^[24]

Pietri et al, 2020 in Systematic review included Probiotic therapy among patients undergoing fixed orthodontic Therapy. They result showed that Probiotics exhibit antimicrobial activity against oral pathogenic bacteria.^[25]

Mechanisms of Action

Probiotics act through multiple pathways:

- 1. Immune modulation:** Interact with dendritic cells and T-helper cells (Th1/Th2), enhancing pathogen clearance.
- 2. Microbiota modulation:** Produce bacteriocins and antimicrobial compounds; compete for adhesion sites.^[26]
- 3. Barrier function enhancement:** Strengthen intestinal and oral mucosa, promote tight junctions, mucin, and IgA production.^[27]
- 4. Neuroimmune regulation:** Influence the enteric and central nervous systems via neurotransmitter modulation.^[28]

5. Cholesterol-lowering effects: Convert cholesterol to copro-stanol, incorporate it into membranes, and stimulate bile acid synthesis.^[29]

Delivery Methods Include

Vectors of administration impact effectiveness. Dairy products like milk and yogurt are optimal due to buffering capacity, calcium content, and support for casein phosphopeptides. Slow-release formulations (e.g., Yakult *Lactobacillus paracasei*) maintain efficacy over 24 hours, reducing *Streptococcus mutans* and extracellular polysaccharides.^[30,31]

Frequency and dosage: 10–10¹⁰ CFU per application, typically once to twice daily for 3–12 weeks.

Applications of Probiotics in Periodontal Health

Commercial Probiotics for Periodontal Disease Management

Several probiotics have been clinically tested for their effects on periodontal disease

- **Bifidumbacterin, Acilact, Vitanar:** Contain live bacteria targeting gingivitis and mild periodontitis.
- **GUM PerioBalance (Sunstar):** Contains two strains of *Lactobacillus reuteri* designed to combat periodontopathogens. Each lozenge delivers at least 2 × 10¹⁰ live cells of *L. reuteri*.
- **PeriBiotic:** A fluoride-free toothpaste with *Lactobacillus paracasei*, promoting oral microbial balance.^[32]
- **Proalana-b Sparlife And Enterogermina Sanofi:** Oral suspensions and capsules designed to support microbial balance.
- **Prodentis Lozenge:** Contains *L. reuteri* DSM 17938 and ATCC PTA 5289, at least 1 × 10¹⁰ CFU per lozenge.

- **Bacipro, Tufpro, Procillus :** Oral suspensions, capsules, and granules from different companies targeting microbial modulation.

Safety and Selection Criteria of Oral Probiotics

While probiotics are generally safe, systemic safety is crucial, as some portion is ingested. Most strains are classified as GRAS (Generally Recognized as Safe) by the FDA.

Ideal characteristics for oral probiotics include

- High viability and resistance to acid
- Ability to adhere to oral surfaces
- Interaction with the immune system
- Human origin and nonpathogenic
- Resistance to processing
- Influence on local metabolism

Effective doses: 1 × 10¹⁰ to 1 × 10¹¹ CFU, with rare cases of infections (bacteremia, fungemia, endocarditis) mostly in immunocompromised individuals.

Precautions

- *Lactobacillus* probiotics may be contraindicated for milk lactose-allergic patients.
- Immunocompromised patients, chemotherapy recipients, and those with short-bowel syndrome should use caution.

Probiotics and Peri-Implant Health

Peri-implantitis shows a highly diverse microbiome, including aerobic and anaerobic bacteria. Common pathogens include *T. denticola*, *P. intermedia*, *C. rectus*, and *Staphylococcus warneri*. Viral components like cytomegalo virus and Epstein-Barr virus are also prevalent.^[33]

Probiotics help Maintain Peri-implant Health By

By downregulating IL-17 pathways, probiotics reduce neutrophil activity, tissue damage, and bone loss, supporting both periodontal and peri-implant health.

However, Linares A et al, 2023 in her Systemic Review included three types of adjunctive measures Local systemic antibiotics and probiotics, they found that Systemic

antimicrobials showed significantly greater reduction in PD and BoP.^[34]

Future Directions in Probiotic Therapy

Genetically Modified and Polystrain Probiotics

1. Genetically modified probiotics

- Reducing harmful traits in pathogens, e.g., creating less cariogenic *S. mutans* by removing lactate hydrogenase genes.
- Enhancing beneficial microbes, e.g., engineering *L. paracasei* to target *P. gingivalis* with specific antibodies.^[35]

2. Polystrain probiotics

- Combining multiple strains species to create synergistic effects for microbial balance and immunity enhancement.

3. Patho-Biotechnology:

It was introduced by Sletor and Hill (2007) includes

- Using weakened pathogens as vaccines
- Extracting and applying pathogen-specific immunogenic proteins^[36]

4. Designer probiotics:

It involve engineering probiotics with receptor-mimicking structures to block or neutralize pathogens.

Conclusion

The oral microbiome plays a central role in maintaining oral and systemic health, and its imbalance contributes to periodontal diseases. While traditional therapies like scaling and root planing are essential, probiotics, prebiotics, synbiotics, and postbiotics offer promising adjunctive strategies. Strains such as *Lactobacillus reuteri*, *L. casei*, and *Bifidobacterium animalis* help reduce pathogens, control inflammation, and improve tissue health. Prebiotics support beneficial microbial growth, while synbiotics and postbiotics enhance effectiveness and stability. Integrating these microbial-based therapies with conventional treatment provides a holistic, targeted, and sustainable approach to periodontal care, with personalized and designer probiotics representing the future of precision oral health management.

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